

Two stage biodegradation of pharmaceutical waste water for pollution control

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Abstract : Treatment of pharmaceutical waste water by chemical process following biological and tertiary processes was studied. The system was optimized and depletion of COD and BOD was achieved by two stage activated sludge process. The feeding of chemically treated waste water in first stage aerobic reactor on 24 hourly basis proved to be effective in achieving the target of depletion of initial pollutants load to its maximum depletion level. The MLSS level of 4000–4500 mg/L in aerobic reactor was found to be more effective in respect to the overall performance of this treatment process. The overall removal rate of COD and BOD in the waste water achieved by this treatment process was up to 99.3%, and the effluent COD and BOD met the Pollution Control Board standard.

Keywords : Pharmaceutical waste water, biodegradation, COD, BOD, effluent, bioremediation.

Introduction

India is one of the leading exporters of pharmaceuticals in the world. Different pharmaceutical industry produces a large number of antibiotics and discharges waste into sewers. Chemical synthesis processes of the pharmaceutical industry often produce high strength waste water that seasonally changes in character and quantity¹. Most pharmaceutical substances are biologically active and hydrophilic in nature. Only few industries have their own treatment plant for checking the effects on living beings, public health, water and soil. Many medicine manufacturing factories discharge their effluent into nearest land or river through sewers². This process may alter the physical and chemical composition of water and soil. Due to this increment it is essential to find out an effective treatment of waste waters as well as for pollution control. The waste water treatment must be effective and economic.

Pharmaceutical waste water is usually characterized by both a considerable fraction of organic substrates i.e. high BOD, COD and DOC values. These are biodegradable by aerobic and anaerobic treatment as well as a fraction that is practically inert toward conventional bioremediation. Although integrated chemical biochemical systems seemed to be feasible for the remediation of compounds present in the effluent, pharmaceutical waste

water is generally being treated via anaerobic/aerobic biological methods due to cost and technical advantages. Now a days, there has been a growing concern over the contamination of the environment with pharmaceutical residues. Their widespread appearance in the aquatic environment is because of their high consumption and incomplete removal during waste water treatment.

The aim and objectives of the study was (i) to characterize the pharmaceutical waste water effluents, (ii) to elucidate the efficiency of treatment process including chemical followed by biological and tertiary treatment and (iii) to find out percent depletion in TSS, COD and BOD in effluent after treatment.

Materials and method :

This study was carried out on mixed waste water from PTS Packers and Provider Pvt. Ltd., a leading Pharmaceuticals Company, producing bulk drug as well as formulated drug situated at Sangkhola, Singtam in East Sikim. At first, pH, TSS, COD, BOD of mixed waste water were measured. The same parameters were measured after treatment. The instrument used in the experiment was Jar Test Apparatus, D. O. Meter, spectrophotometer, COD digester, pH meter, Pilot scale plant etc.

In this study the treatment process involved chemical treatment followed by biological and tertiary treatment

process³. The chemicals used in treatments are given below.

Chemicals used : (1) Sodium hydroxide solution (5%), (2) alum solution (10%), (3) non-ionic poly electrolyte (1%), (4) urea, (5) diammonium phosphate and (6) activated carbon.

Principle of treatment :

(A) *Chemical treatment* :

Chemical treatment by solution of NaOH and alum :

NaOH solution was added to adjust lower level of pH and after this lime would be added for maintaining the alkalinity required to react with alum as well as to increase the pH value. Then alum solution was added to water in the presence of alkalinity, which produced aluminum hydroxide as gelatinous floc, that settled slowly through the waste water and swept out the suspended solid as well as reduced the level of COD and BOD and finally neutralization of waste water was done.

When alum solution was added to waste water containing calcium and magnesium bicarbonate alkalinity, the reaction that occurred may be illustrated as below.

The insoluble aluminum hydroxide was a gelatinous floc that settled slowly through the waste water, swept out suspended material and produced other changes.

The low dose of non-ionic poly electrolyte brought about particle aggregation and finally enhanced the precipitation i.e. settling process.

(B) *Microbiological treatment* :

Two stages activated sludge process – As the effluent was biodegradable, biological treatment required to remove biodegradable load. Aeration was used for transferring oxygen to biological treatment process. Certain microorganism oxidized biological phenols in activated sludge process. Under proper pH 7.0 to 7.5 the biodegradable organic substance of waste water was completely degraded by biological oxidization, part of it was oxidized while rest of that converted into biological mass in the biological reactor. The end product of the metabolism was either low molecular weight gas or liquid.

(C) *Aerobic attached growth treatment processes* :

Aerobic attached growth biological treatment processes usually were used to remove organic matter found in waste water. They were also used to achieve nitrification (the conversion of nitrogen in the form of ammonia to ni-

trate). The attached growth processes included the trickling filter, the roughing filter, rotating biological contactor, and fixed-bed nitrification reactor.

(D) *Tertiary treatment* :

The tertiary treatment was applied using adsorption by activated carbon to remove remaining organic constituent as well as odour of effluent.

Systems description :

The mixed water was first brought to an equalization tank. From equalization tank the effluent was lifted to Continuous Stirred Tank Reactor No. 1 (CSTR-1) where NaOH solution was added followed by alum solution in CSTR-2 and non-ionic poly electrolyte solution in CSTR-3 to the effluent. The effluent passed to Primary Settling Tank No. 1 for proper precipitation. The precipitation was settled at the bottom of the tank as sludge, which was brought to sludge drying bed by gravity.

The clear liquid from Primary Settling Tank No. 1 was brought to Aeration Tank No. 1 where primary aerobic biodegradation of biodegradable organic part of the effluent occurred. The overflow from Aeration Tank No. 1 was brought to Secondary Settling Tank No. 1 where biological mass would be settled at the bottom. A part of the sludge was recycled (by a sludge pump) back to the Aeration Tank No. 1 for recycling and other part was brought to sludge drying bed. The clear effluent from the Secondary Settling Tank No. 1 was brought to Aeration Tank No. 2 where second stage aerobic biodegradation occurred. The overflow from Aeration Tank No. 2 was brought to Secondary Settling Tank No. 2, where biological mass was settled at the bottom. A part of the biological sludge was taken back to the Aeration Tank No. 2 to maintain the MLSS of the effluent at desired level. The other part was brought to sludge drying bed.

The clear liquid from Secondary Settling Tank No. 2 was passed through trickling filter and finally adsorption was done by carbon beds in series. The schematic diagram is given in Fig. 1.

Results and discussion

Although pharmaceutical waste water may contain diverse organic materials that cannot be readily degraded, in addition to physicochemical processes^{4,5}, biological treatment is still a viable choice for treatment^{1,6,7}. However, due to the high strength, it is not feasible and economical to treat this kind of waste water using a single-stage aerobic biological treatment process. Instead, a com-

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of treatment plant.

bination of anaerobic and aerobic processes is preferred and appears to be more effective in removing high-strength organic matter. Table 1 shows the water quality of the mixed waste used for these treatments. Changes in the process parameters after treatment are depicted in Table 2. (%) Depletion of pollutants in different steps are given in Table 3.

Table 1. Characteristics of mixed effluent before treatment

pH	2.88
TSS (mg/L)	650
COD (mg/L)	10500
BOD (mg/L)	3500

Table 2. Characteristics of mixed effluent after treatment

Water sample	pH	TSS (mg/L)	COD (mg/L)	BOD (mg/L)
1. After chemical treatment ^a and pH adjustment	8.0	280	6500	2450
2. After 1st biological treatment				
(i) After 24 h	7.8	160	2800	980
(ii) After 48 h	7.5	120	1050	350
3. After 2nd biological treatment				
(i) After 72 h	7.5	80	430	145
(ii) After 96 h	7.3	60	160	50
4. After trickling filter	7.2	50	100	35
5. After activated carbon	7.1	30	80	25

^aTreatment : 1 L of sample + 25 ml 5% of NaOH + 20 ml 10% alum + 5 ml 0.1% non-ionic poly electrolyte + NaOH (for pH adjustment) – Supernatant for biological treatment.

Chemical treatment :

The system included waste water neutralization, pH adjustment. The goal of the system was to reduce suspended solid as well the level of COD and BOD. Pharmaceutical industries produce a wide variety of products using both organic and inorganic substances as raw materials, generating a large quantity of complex toxic organic liquid wastes containing high concentrations of inorganic TDS⁸. In the present study an attempt had been made by applying of chemical coagulant alum in the presence of alkali, as a pretreatment which produced aluminum hydroxide as gelatinous floc and also low dose of non-ionic poly electrolyte was added for particle aggregation. So, finally these enhanced the precipitation i.e. settling process.

The waste water with a TSS value of 650 mg/L was reduced to 280 mg/L (Tables 1 and 2 and Fig. 2). 56.9% depletion of TSS value was observed in this step which helped in increasing the efficiency for achieving better biological treatment (Table 3). According to Wang *et al.*⁹, internal micro-electrolysis and coagulation served as the pretreatment for the waste water before biological treatment to reduce the contaminants' toxicity to microbes and improve the biodegradability of waste water to guarantee the smooth operation of the biological process. This study was also similar to the studies by Kabdaşlı *et al.*¹⁰, Samuel Suman Raj and Anjaneyulu⁸. Due to the removal

Fig. 2. Showing differences of TSS values before and after treatment.

Fig. 3. Showing differences of COD values before and after treatment.

of the solid particles the initial COD and BOD was also reduced by 38.1 and 30% respectively (Table 3).

Table 3. (%) Depletion of pollutants in different steps

Water sample	TSS (%)	COD (%)	BOD (%)
1. After chemical treatment ^a	56.9	38.1	30.0
2. After 1st biological treatment (after 48 h)	24.6	51.9	60.0
3. After 2nd biological treatment (after 96 h)	9.2	8.5	8.6
4. After trickling filter	1.5	0.6	0.4
5. After activated carbon	3.1	0.2	0.3
Total	95.3	99.3	99.3

Microbiological treatment :

In conventional waste water treatment plants, a combination of biological treatment with high sludge residence times and ozonation of the effluent seems to be the most promising technology. Biological treatment was the main body of the whole process which took main role in removing COD and BOD. Understanding the biological transformation of pharmaceutical waste, it is essential for accurately determining their ultimate environmental fate¹¹. To start the operation, diluted mixed pharmaceutical waste water, the pH of which had been adjusted to 7-7.5 with COD of 6500 mg/L was introduced. Appreciable COD and BOD removal did not occur within the first 24 h of micro biological treatment. But in case of 48 h, depletion was 51.9% and 60% for COD and BOD respectively (Table 3). TSS value was also lower. Mudrack *et al.*¹², attributed the adaptability of the biological treatment system to frequent changes in composition, flow rate and

Fig. 4. Showing differences of BOD values before and after treatment.

(1) After chemical treatment^a, (2) after 1st biological treatment (after 48 h), (3) after 2nd biological treatment (after 96 h), (4) after trickling filter, (5) after activated carbon.

Fig. 5. Showing (%) depletion of pollutants in different steps following Table 3.

toxic substance mainly to the multiplicity of species in the biogenesis of the activated sludge. Mascolo *et al.*¹³ reported the biodegradability of pharmaceutical waste by during aerobic biological treatment.

Aerobic attached growth treatment processes :

The biological treatment requires contact of the biomass with the substrate. Aerobic techniques, such as activated sludge process, trickling filters, oxidation ponds¹⁴, roughing filter, rotating biological contactor, fixed-bed nitrification reactor and aerated lagoons, with more or less intense mixing devices, have been successfully used for industrial waste water treatment. Using the attached growth processes include the trickling filter, the roughing filter, rotating biological contactor, and fixed-bed nitrification reactor, BOD and COD removals were remarkably reduced. Depletion of TSS, COD and BOD values after trickling filter were 1.5, 0.6 and 0.4% respectively (Table 3). It was also observed that % depletion of COD and BOD increased according to the different increased level of MLSS (mg/L). The MLSS level of 4000–4500 mg/L in aerobic reactor was found to be more effective in respect to the overall performance of this treatment process (Fig. 6 and Table 4).

Fig. 6. Showing (%) depletion of COD and BOD in response to MLSS level (mg/L).

Table 4. (%) Depletion of COD and BOD in response to MLSS level (mg/L)

Sl. no.	MLSS (mg/L)	COD (%)	BOD (%)
1.	1000–1500	37.5	43.7
2.	2000–2500	39.3	43.9
3.	3000–3500	51.5	63.4
4.	4000–4500	75.75	80.5

Tertiary treatment :

The addition of activated carbon powder to the mixed liquor of activated sludge treatment plants can be used to remove the color, odor from waste water, to protect the treatment plant against toxic components in the influent,

and to improve the removal of non-biodegradable chemical oxygen demand (COD). Wang *et al.*⁹, adopted activated carbon adsorption as the post-treatment process to further remove the remaining non-biodegradable particles. Malik *et al.*¹⁵, reported for dosages of activated carbon in the range of 50–150 mg/L, the removal efficiencies for BOD increased from 27–70% to 76–94% while those for COD increased from 16–64% to 72–92.5%. In our present study, TSS, COD, BOD depletion of about 3.1, 0.2, 0.3% obtained with powdered activated carbon treatment were observed (Table 3).

Conclusions :

A study on selection of appropriate treatment techniques for pharmaceutical waste has been conducted. Biological treatment was the main choice for treatment due to its cost-effectiveness and environmental acceptability. From the above experiment, the best treatment process was finalized which will be able to deplete the pollution load to below the permissible limit of Pollution Control Board.

So, it might be concluded from the study that chemical treatment followed by continuous biological treatment with intake of chemically treated effluent on continuous basis to Aeration Tank after holding tank was the best technique for controlling pollution due to Pharmaceutical waste water.

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